

Evaluation and development of DGT as a monitoring tool at an active uranium industrial site

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The Orano Tricastin industrial platform, located in the Drôme and Vaucluse Departments, encompasses several chemical processes and uranium enrichment activities preceding the final stage of fuel assembly fabrication for nuclear power plant reactors.

In order to assess the potential environmental impact of these activities, an extensive monitoring program is performed by Orano, consisting of the analysis of air, water, soil, fauna and flora on the site and in the surrounding area. The analysis of groundwater is of particular interest due to the shallow ground water table and the connections with the surface water. Several hundreds of piezometers have been installed on and around the site.

The aim of the study is to evaluate whether DGT can be used as a long-term monitoring tool for uranium in ground water and river water, in order to obtain time integrated averaged concentrations. A preliminary expedition was performed in March 2018, in which DGTs containing Chelex[®] resin were deployed in eight piezometers for 24h and in the Gaffiere river, flowing through the site, DGT units with Chelex resin were deployed for 24h up to one month. Point samples were taken at the start and end of each deployment for comparison and water samples were taken to characterize the water composition. A comparison was also made with DGT containing Iontosorb Oxin[®] resin, containing 8-hydroxyquinoline functional groups.

The preliminary expedition revealed the need to determine the diffusion boundary layer thickness for quantification of uranium concentrations in piezometers and river water and showed a non-perfect sink behavior of uranium in the calcium bicarbonate rich waters for a deployment time of longer than two days.

In order to develop the technique for its application in uranium monitoring for longer time periods, laboratory tests were performed using different resins (such as Diphonix, Dow Piwba, Chelex, Iontosorb and mixed resins), different diffusion gel thicknesses, single and double resin gel layers, using the river water as deployment solution. Uptake kinetics and competitive uptake of Ca and Mg on the resin gels were evaluated.

The results of these experiments will be presented at the conference.